

Suomen ympäristökeskus
Finlands miljöcentral
Finnish Environment Institute

Letter of Support for BLISS Innovation Action Proposal

To the European Commission,

FINMARI is a distributed, multiplatform and multidisciplinary Research Infrastructure coordinated by Finnish Environment Institute (Syke). It combines the major components of Finnish marine research community and creates solid knowledge base for the protection of the Baltic Sea. FINMARI has been on the Finnish National Infrastructure Roadmap since 2014. FINMARI partners are responsible on national monitoring of the health of Baltic Sea waters and run research labs and research vessels to understand how marine systems respond to changes.

FINMARI strongly supports the BLISS (Building Living Labs for Island Sustainable Solutions) Innovation Action proposal.

FINMARI recognizes the valuable synergies between energy transition and marine sustainability on European islands. BLISS offers complementary solutions that strengthen island resilience. We see significant potential for collaboration between our networks, sharing best practices in island sustainability transitions. The BLISS project's replication strategy aligns with our experience in scaling successful island innovations.

Syke FINMARI coordination team endorses BLISS and looks forward to exploring partnership opportunities.

Kind regards,

In Helsinki, 15.9.2025

Dr. Jukka Seppälä

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